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Research Article

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION
FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
ABALOPARATIDE AND TERIPARATIDE IN COMBINED
DOSAGE FORM BY USING RP-HPLC METHOD****Dr. Gampa Vijay Kumar^{1,2} D.Rajendhar³**^{1,2} Professor and Head, Dept. of Pharmacy, KGR Institute of Technology and Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy, Telangana, India.³ KGR Institute of Technology and Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy, Telangana, India.**Abstract**

New method was established for simultaneous estimation of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide by using ACE C18 column (4.6×150mm) 5 μ , flow rate was 1.2 ml/min, mobile phase ratio was (70:30 v/v) methanol:Phosphate buffer pH 3 (pH was adjusted with orthophosphoric acid), detection wavelength was 240nm. The instrument used was Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20 Solution. The retention times were found to be 2.344 mins and 3.284 mins. The % purity of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide was found to be 101.27% and 99.97% respectively. The system suitability parameters for Abaloparatide and Teriparatide such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 4668, 1.3 and 6089 and 1.2, the resolution was found to be 6.0. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study for Abaloparatide and Teriparatide was found in concentration range of 50 μ g-250 μ g and 5 μ g-50 μ g and correlation coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % recovery was found to be 99.56% and 99.48%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.2 and 0.2, % RSD for intermediate precision was 0.2 and 0.1 respectively. The precision study was precise, robust, and repeatable. LOD value was 3.17 and 5.68, and LOQ value was 0.0172 and 0.2125 respectively. Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide in API and Pharmaceutical dosage form.

Keywords: ACE C18 column, Abaloparatide and Teriparatide, RP-HPLC**Corresponding author:****Dr. Gampa Vijaya kumar,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Abaloparatide (brand name Tymlos; formerly BA058) is a parathyroid hormone-related protein (PTHrP) analog drug used to treat osteoporosis. Like the related drug teriparatide, and unlike bisphosphonates, it is an anabolic (i.e., bone growing) agent. A subcutaneous injection formulation of the drug has completed a Phase III trial for osteoporosis. This single study found a decrease in fractures.

Teriparatide is a recombinant protein form of parathyroid hormone consisting of the first (N-

terminus) 34 amino acids, which is the bioactive portion of the hormone. It is an effective anabolic (i.e., bone growing) agent used in the treatment of some forms of osteoporosis. It is also occasionally used off-label to speed fracture healing. Teriparatide is identical to a portion of human parathyroid hormone (PTH) and intermittent use activates osteoblasts more than osteoclasts, which leads to an overall increase in bone.

Teriparatide**MATERIALS AND METHOD AND INSTRUMENTATION**

Ortho phosphoric acid, Acetonitrile, Methanol, Water, KH_2PO_4 , K_2HPO_4

HPLC- Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20 Solution, U.V double beam spectrometer, UV 3000+, U.V win soft ware, Lab India, Digital weighing balance (sensitivity 5mg), pH meter, Sonicator

Chromatographic conditions**Trial -5 (optimised method)****Chromatographic conditions**

Column	:	ACE C18 (4.6×150 mm) 5.0 μm
Column temperature	:	Ambient
Wavelength	:	240 nm
Mobile phase ratio	:	70:30 Methanol: Phosphate buffer
Flow rate	:	1.2 ml/min
Auto sampler temperature	:	Ambient
Injection volume	:	10 μl
Run time	:	10.0 minutes

Fig.No.1. Chromatogram showing trial-5 injections

Observation

The separation was good, peak shape was good, so we conclude that there is no required for reduce the retention times of peaks, so it is taken as final method.

Preparation of the individual Abaloparatide standard preparation

10 mg of abaloparatide working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2 ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette out 1.5 ml from the above stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of the individual teriparatide standard preparation

10 mg of teriparatide working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to Dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette out 3 ml from the above stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of the Abaloparatide and Teriparatide standard and sample solution Sample solution preparation:

10 mg of Abaloparatide and 1 mg Teriparatide tablet powder were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask, add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and making volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette 10ml of the

above stock solution into a 100ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Standard solution preparation

10 mg Abaloparatide and 1 mg Teriparatide working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution). Further pipette out 1ml of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

METHOD VALIDATION:

1. Specificity

The system suitability for specificity was carried out to determine whether there is any interference of any impurities in retention time of analytical peak. The specificity was performed by injecting blank.

2. Linearity

10 mg of Abaloparatide and 1 mg of Teriparatide working standard were accurately weighed and were transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask, add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

3. Range

Based on precision, linearity and accuracy data it can be concluded that the assay method is precise, linear and accurate in the range of 50 μ g/ml-250 μ g/ml and 5 μ g/ml-25 μ g/ml of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide respectively.

4. Accuracy

10mg of Abaloparatide and 1mg of Teriparatide working standard were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution).Further pipette out 1 ml of the above stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

5. Precision**Repeatability**

10 mg of Abaloparatide and 1 mg of Teriparatide working standard were accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. Further pipette out 1ml of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as ruggedness) of the method, precision was performed on different days by using different make column of same dimensions.

6. Limit of detection (LOD)

LOD's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) at levels approximating the LOD according to the formula. The standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

7. Limit of quantification

LOQ's can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the response (SD) and the slope of the calibration curve (S) according to the formula. Again, the standard deviation of the response can be determined based on the standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines.

8. Robustness

As part of the robustness, deliberate change in the flow rate, mobile phase composition was made to evaluate the impact on the method.

9. System suitability

10 mg of Abaloparatide and 1 mg of Teriparatide working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and add about 2ml of diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution).Further pipette out 1ml of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide from the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Linearity****Table.No.1. Linearity Results for Abaloparatide:**

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	50 ppm	471543
2	II	100 ppm	656277
3	III	150 ppm	794999
4	IV	200 ppm	946124
5	V	250 ppm	1002139
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

$$\text{Abaloparatide } r^2 = 0.999$$

Fig.No.2. showing Calibration graph Abaloparatide

S.No	Linearity Level	Concentration	Area
1	I	5ppm	56472
2	II	10 ppm	73841
3	III	15ppm	92655
4	IV	20ppm	111541
5	V	25ppm	130567
Correlation Coefficient			0.999

Table.No.2. Linearity Results for teriparatide:

Fig.No 3. Showing calibration graph for teriparatide

$$\text{Teriparatide } r^2 = 0.999$$

ACCURACY:**Table.No.3. Showing accuracy results for Abaloparatide**

%Concentration (at specification level)	Average area	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean recovery
50%	656659	5	4.96	99.91%	99.56%
100%	1304258	10	9.98	99.18%	
150%	1854608	15	15.02	99.60%	

Table.No.4. Showing accuracy results for teriparatide

%Concentration (at specification level)	Average area	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean recovery
50%	65312	0.5	0.99	99.53%	99.47%
100%	124509	1.0	1.05	99.38%	
150%	178517	1.5	1.495	99.52%	

PRECISION:**Table.No.5. Showing% RSD results for Abaloparatide****Peak Name : Abaloparatide**

	Peak name	RT	AREA	HEIGHT
1	Abaloparatide	2.343	1302729	248455
2	Abaloparatide	2.344	1309759	248699
3	Abaloparatide	2.344	1302947	249526
4	Abaloparatide	2.345	1303977	246695
5	Abaloparatide	2.345	1303236	250012
MEAN			1304529.8	
STD.DEV.			2961.1	
%RSD			0.2	

Table.No.6. Showing %RSD results for Teriparatide**Peak Name : Teriparatide**

	Peak name	Rt	Area	Height
1	Teriparatide	3.285	124263	19458
2	Teriparatide	3.287	124487	19634
3	Teriparatide	3.287	124175	19600
4	Teriparatide	3.288	124894	19327
5	Teriparatide	3.288	124495	19540
Mean			124462.7	
Std.dev.			278.6	
%RSD			0.2	

Intermediate precision/Ruggedness**Table.No.7. Showing results for intermediate precision of Abaloparatide****Peak Name : Abaloparatide**

	Peak name	RT	AREA	HEIGHT
1	Abaloparatide	2.342	1305937	247870
2	Abaloparatide	2.343	1306476	246764
3	Abaloparatide	2.344	1304520	247140
4	Abaloparatide	2.344	1300148	247280
5	Abaloparatide	2.345	1308271	250012
MEAN			1305070.2	
STD.DEV.			3061.8	
%RSD			0.2	

Table.No.8. Showing results for intermediate precision of Teriparatide

Peak Name : Teriparatide

	PEAK NAME	RT	AREA	HEIGHT
1	Teriparatide	3.278	122962	19165
2	Teriparatide	3.281	122487	19115
3	Teriparatide	3.281	122632	19073
4	Teriparatide	3.281	122626	19003
5	Teriparatide	3.283	122702	19123
Mean			122681.8	
Std.dev.			174.8	
%RSD			0.1	

Detection limit

Table.No.9 Showing results for Limit of Detection

Drug name	Standard deviation(σ)	Slope(s)	LOD(μg)
Abaloparatide	382625.50	572175863	3.17
teriparatide	5862.40	467579210	0.0172

Quantitation limit

Table.No.10. Showing results for Limit of Quantitation

Drug name	Standard deviation(σ)	Slope(s)	LOQ(μg)
Abaloparatide	381727.80	583265980	5.80
teriparatide	5681.30	469828490	0.212

ROBUSTNESS:

Fig.No.4. Chromatogram showing less flow rate 0.8ml/min

Fig.No.5. Chromatogram showing less flow rate 1.2 ml/min

Table.No.11. Showing system suitability results for Abaloparatide

S. No	Flow rate (ml/min)	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	5339	1.4
2	1	4668	1.3
3	1.2	5216	1.4

Table.No.12 Showing system suitability results for teriparatide

S. No	Flow rate (ml/min)	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	0.8	7036	1.3
2	1	6089	1.2
3	1.2	6998	1.3

Fig.No.6 Chromatogram showing more organic phase ratio

Fig.No.7. Chromatogram showing less organic phase ratio

Table.No.13. Showing system suitability results for Abaloparatide

S. No	Change in organic composition in the mobile phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	5 % less	6232	1.4
2	*Actual	4668	1.3
3	5 % more	6387	1.4

Table.No.14. Showing system suitability results for teriparatide

S. No	Change in organic composition in the mobile phase	System suitability results	
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	5 % less	5437	1.3
2	*Actual	6089	1.2
3	5 % more	4817	1.2

8. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

A new method was established for simultaneous estimation of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide by RP-HPLC method. The chromatographic conditions were successfully developed for the separation of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide by using ACE C18 column (4.6×150mm) 5 μ , flow rate was 1.2 ml/min, mobile phase ratio was (70:30 v/v) methanol:Phosphate buffer pH 3 (pH was adjusted with orthophosphoric acid), detection wavelength was 240nm. The instrument used was Shimadzu, model No. SPD-20MA LC+20AD, Software- LC-20 Solution. The retention times were found to be 2.344 mins and 3.284 mins. The % purity of Abaloparatide and Teriparatide was found to be 101.27% and 99.97% respectively. The system suitability

parameters for Abaloparatide and Teriparatide such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 4668, 1.3 and 6089 and 1.2, the resolution was found to be 6.0. The analytical method was validated according to ICH guidelines (ICH, Q2 (R1)). The linearity study in Abaloparatide and Teriparatide was found in concentration range of 50 μ g-250 μ g and 5 μ g-50 μ g and correlation coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.999 and 0.999, % recovery was found to be 99.56% and 99.48%, %RSD for repeatability was 0.2 and 0.2, % RSD for intermediate precision was 0.2 and 0.1 respectively. The precision study was precise, robust, and repeatable. LOD value was 3.17 and 5.68, and LOQ value was 0.0172 and 0.2125 respectively. Hence the suggested RP-HPLC method can be used for routine analysis of Abaloparatide and

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